

Addressing the Challenges of Integrating Business Education into Nigeria's Educational System: Educational Planners Concern

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Abstract

In recent times, graduates who have completed their studies in the field of Business education in Nigeria tertiary institutions seems to encounter difficulties securing employment opportunities upon graduating from tertiary institutions in Nigeria due to the prevailing perception of the program as being oriented towards blue-collar occupations rather than white-collar professions. The objective of the study is to identify and address the challenges encountered in integrating business education into Nigeria's educational system from the perspective of educational planners and to recommend innovating solutions to the current challenges facing business education programme in Nigeria tertiary institutions by the educational planners. It is to this that the researcher tends to investigate the challenges encountered in integrating business education into Nigeria's educational system, from the perspective of educational planners. Despite the significance and economic advancement of business education programme in Nigeria tertiary institutions in fostering economic growth and equipping students with essential skills, its integration into the Nigerian educational system seems to face significant challenges. These challenges include Business Education expert seems not to be fully involved in the planning, designing, reviewing and implementation of the Business education curriculum, inadequate fund allocation by the Federal government into business education programme at different levels, Unqualified, Competent and Experienced Business Educators. This research aims to identify and analyze these challenges, offering innovative solutions by educational planners to address them. By Developing a clear, long-term strategic plan which aligns with Nigeria tertiary institution mission and vision, ensures adequate funding and updates of business education curriculum to reflect current industry trends and technological advancements. The researcher concludes by saying that the research will provide valuable insights for government, educators, curriculum planners and stakeholders contributing to the effective integration of business education programme and support to national development.

Keywords: Business Education, Challenges, Innovations, Solution and Educational Planners

Introduction

Business Education is a course of study in Nigeria tertiary institutions which encompasses different options which are Accounting, entrepreneurial, Marketing and Office Technology and Management (OTM) which holds employment prospects for her graduates in sectors such as but not limited to education, financial, industrial, manufacturing, distribution, managerial settings as well as Information and Communication Technology (ICT). According to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) defined Business Education to be part of Vocational and Technical Education offered in tertiary institutions in Nigeria with the sole aim of imparting necessary skills to individuals to become self-reliant economically. Okoli,

(2010) opined that Business Education is concerned with teaching of knowledge, skills, competencies and attitudes necessary for successful business career and sustainable economy growth and development. Business education refers to a programme of instruction that offers various skills in accounting, marketing and Office Technology and Management (OTM). Major topics include: office practice, book keeping, business mathematics, business communication, secretarial duties, word processing, advertising (Ajisafe, Bolarinwa & Edeh 2015). Ebinga (2014) defined business education as a programme of study which offers students who wish to pursue a career in business an opportunity to develop skills, abilities and understanding that will enable them to enter, perform and progress in business occupation after graduating from high school or the university.

Innovation requires the ability to think creatively, solve problems, and spot market opportunities. The ability of one's to identify an opportunity were people sees nothing, ability to solve problems and carve out something from nothing in any given place. Innovation is the process of developing new products, services, or processes that create value and solve customer problems (Nicholas, Donagh, & Stefan, 2020). Innovation drives employment and development using the available resources in any given place. That's why graduates who have completed their studies in the field of Business education in Nigeria tertiary institutions seems to encounter difficulties securing employment opportunities upon graduating from tertiary institutions in Nigeria due to the prevailing perception of the program as being oriented towards blue-collar occupations rather than white-collar professions. It was because Business education students makes use of their brain and hand in engaging in skills such as weaving, trading, barbing, hair dressing, etcetera to grow themselves in-order to be self-employed and create. According to Hassan, Ore and Ayeni (2024) discussed extensively that graduates of business education are job creators and not job seekers. Ogwu, Omeje and Nwokenna (2014) in Hassan et.al (2024) asserted that business education students could create jobs in the areas of weaving, trading, barbing, hair dressing, making of molds, music, and so on.

Business Education programme although has been introduced and implemented in the university programmes of study for more than three decades now but the graduates of the programme are still faced with the problem of unemployment in the country despite the promising prospects of the course of study and universities in Nigeria keep producing thousands of theoretical and liberal arts business education graduates with little or no entrepreneurial skills and their potentials for being gainfully employed is uncertain (David & Fabian, 2019). Business education has been defined by various scholars and researchers both locally and internationally but the programme seems facing challenges in bringing new ideas to Nigeria educational tertiary system which makes the educational planners to take it as a concern to them.

In addition, the overall philosophy of the Nigerian education is that education is an instrument for national development; the formulation of ideas, integration for national development, and the interaction of persons and ideas (NPE, 2004). Since the Nigeria education has its philosophy, so also business education has its own philosophy too, it therefore becomes necessary that the challenges of business education programme need to be addressed and challenges needs to be tackled in-order to integrate the programme to fit Nigeria educational system through the innovative point by the educational planners.

Philosophy of Business Education curriculum as stated in Aquah (2014) in Hassan. et.al (2024) includes:

- i. To equip the student with necessary saleable skills that will make them acquire, sustain and grow on their jobs and be self-employed thereby creating jobs for others
- ii. To prepare Business education students for advanced training in business education
- iii. To prepare student for higher studies in Business Education
- iv. To gain the basic knowledge and skills of Business Education
- v. To possess the basic skill requires in office occupation

The philosophy behind business education according to Amoo (2010) is to provide its graduates viz a viz appropriate knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies to become self-employed. People who utilize both human and material resources for optimal productivity are also with the skills to be self-reliant. Business education promotes self-employment through the skill acquisition development and also it is a tool in the hand governments to combat unemployment and reduce poverty in the society.

Objective of the study

1. To identify and address challenges facing business education programme in Nigeria tertiary education; and
2. To recommend innovating solutions to the current challenges facing business education programme in Nigeria tertiary institutions by the educational planners.

Before giving the meaning of what Educational Planning is all about Planning concept needs to be addressed- Planning entails the process of taking a decision ahead of what to do, when to do it, how to do it and who to do it by drafting and building a goal to be achieve at the end. It is also the link between where we are and where we ought to be. According to

Yawe (2010) "planning is the process of determining in advance, what is to be done, including classification of goals, establishment of policies, mapping out of programme and campaigns and determining specific methods or procedures and fixing day-to-day schedules"

Educational planning is a general term which can be seen as applying rational approach across learning process in order to make education more meaningful and effective for the students, teachers and society. According to Ololube, (2013), educational planning in its broadest generic sense is the application of rational systematic analysis to the process of educational development with the aim of making education more effective and efficient in responding to the needs and goals of its students and society. Considering the definitions of educational planning as the process of taking decisions for future action with the view of achieving pre-determined objectives, through optimum use of scarce resources, the process of educational planning could be seen to comprise of three basic functions. It is to this that educational planners are having concern on how business education programme challenges can be addressed.

The educational planners concern in Nigeria educational system particularly in the area of challenges facing business education programme in Nigeria not to fit into current industry demands been the major aims and objective of the programme. The following are the concern of the educational planners:

1. The Fast technology advancement: There has been a fast and growing technology advancement in the Nigeria educational system such as, the artificial intelligence, internets, etc. it has been a concern of the educational planners that the way business education programme has been structured, designed and taught has not been meeting up the demands in the past years due to the way the Curriculum planners has design the curriculum. It has become compulsory and necessary to equip students with the 21st century skills that are needed in the modern office and not the traditional way of equipping them in the past years because of the fast- growing technology in the country.
2. Inadequate Funding of Business Education Programme: there is a growing concern on the part of the educational planners due to the way the government has been funding the programme. The government seems not to fund the programme in a way they ought to which had always hinder the progress of the programme. Because it is when there is funding, that adequate staffing will be made, purchasing of modern equipment, adequate teaching materials, qualified personnel will be employed, and so on but reverse is the case.
3. Skills imparted to business education students are theoretical rather than practical because the business education programme are not fully involved in the designing of the curriculum which has also been a concern to the educational planners
4. The Business education programme quality assurance measures seem to be poor which has also been a concern to the educational planners
5. There has been a low industrial collaboration between the business education experts which has also been a concern to the educational planners

Business education face numerous challenges in addressing and integrating business education programme in Nigeria tertiary educational system. Some of the most significant challenges facing the programme is as follows:

Business Education expert seems not to be fully involved in the planning, designing, reviewing and implementation of the Business education curriculum: According to Aworanti (2015a) tells us that it is regrettable that most vocational education curricula are outdated having been in use for over fifteen years. Looking at this situation closely, it is clear that current business education may not be able to meet the need of industries or employers of labour genuinely. This situation has consequently created a huge gap between business education and industries in Nigeria. This circumstance has consequently engendered a substantial disparity between business education and industry practices in Nigeria. As a result, the difficulties associated with the formulation of a business education curriculum have emerged as a significant concern among business education specialists, particularly due to the prevailing confusion wherein professionals from other fields, such as educational management, economics, ecetera presume they possess the requisite expertise to design the business education curriculum. This confusion has historically impeded the development of a curriculum that effectively addresses the essential skills necessary for students to acquire, which are vital for securing employment or becoming employers themselves. The researcher ultimately posits that this study will yield invaluable insights for policymakers, educators, and relevant stakeholders, thereby facilitating the effective integration of business education programs and contributing to national development. This may be the reason why, Majumdar (2011) asserts that the challenges on how to develop curriculum and training programme that would help to respond to the skills needed by industries seem to be a common concern. Ugbah (2019) identified the following innovative strategies for successful implementation of business education curriculum in universities and colleges of education: Adequate Funding of Business Education Programmes at all Levels, Review of Business Education Course Curriculum, Collaboration between employers of labour and National Universities Commission/Association of Business Educators,

Provision of Modern Equipment and Facilities for Effective Teaching and learning, Public Enlightenment Programmes, Award of Honorary Certificates/Merit Award to Eminent Members, and Financial Support of Business Educators.

Inadequate fund allocation by the Federal government into business education programme at different levels: On poor funding, Akpan, Umanah, Umoudo and Ukut (2014) maintained that poor funding leads inadequate staffing, inadequate workshops equipment is responsible for poor effectiveness of business studies. When they are inadequate allocation of funding by federal government at the tertiary education level in the programme, it becomes a worry to the specialist in the field because it will hinder so many things such as staffing, equipping necessary equipment, getting of materials from conferences, attending seminars and conferences, and so on. Inadequate provision of financial resources has been identified as greatest challenge facing education in Nigeria (Nwadiani & Omoike, 2006; Asiyai, 2015), especially vocational and technical education sector because of its capital intensive nature (Adeyanju, Adekunle, & Osifila, 2007), of which business education programme is a major component. By virtue of this nature, every item within the business education instructional environment is subjected to adequate optimization of financial resources.

Recruitment of unqualified and incompetence Business education specialist: They seem to have been low recruitment of qualified and competence specialist in the field of business education which has seem to continue hindering the programme to meet up with its demand in the country. The recruitment of specialists in the domain of business education appears to be insufficient, characterized by a lack of qualification and competence, which has seemingly perpetuated obstacles for the program in fulfilling its demand within the nation. Du Plessis (2013) defines an out-of-field teacher as a teacher teaching out of their field of qualification, this field might be a specific subject or year level. Interestingly, out-of-field teaching is not a Nigeria problem alone; it happens even in developed countries like U.S, Australia and even in South Africa. Du Plessis, Carroll and Gillies (2014) cited that 16% and 30% of science teachers in Australia and South Africa respectively. In Nigeria it is a common practice to see a qualified teacher teaching a subject he/she was never trained for and at that point such teacher becomes unqualified. Consequently, individuals from diverse academic disciplines frequently assert that business education is a subject that can be imparted by anyone, a notion that has consistently posed challenges and concerns within this field. Du Plessis et al. (2014) opinion was that out-of-field teachers are still in the process of developing, and they are less suited to teach subjects they had no qualification. This infers that employing any graduate aside those who studied education to the teacher is not proper. This situation has led to a predominance of theoretical concepts being taught, rather than practical theories, thereby engendering a substantial disconnect between business education graduates and the industry upon their graduation from Nigerian institutions. Inadequate Practical Materials: Business education programme is a practical oriented course and not theoretical course but the nature of the country and curriculum planners seems to draw the plan to be a theoretical course which has hinder the program to meet up and address the poverty situation of the economy because if a graduate has been taught necessary skills to acquired, he/she will become an employer of labour which will assist in reducing the unemployment challenges in the country. Research by Adebayo and Ajibade (2018) in the Journal of Educational Research and Reviews points out the issue of inadequate infrastructure in business education institutions. This includes outdated facilities and a lack of modern technology, impacting the quality of education delivery. Olaleye (2009) noted that the various Federal Government programmes on eradication of poverty have failed because graduates of the education system lack the practical skills which can be acquired through Entrepreneurship Education Programme. To make business education relevant the followings must be done:

Lack of updated and Functional Libraries for expert: There seem to have been dilapidated and non- equipped libraries of business education programme. The experts seem not to update the programme library because of so many challenges in the programme such as funding. When you get to the programme libraries onewill find that books of 1990s, early 2000s are kept in the library shelves instead of the current 21st century books. In support of this, Aworanti (2015) observed that the basic infrastructural facilities have declined both in quality and quantity. Even where these infrastructural facilities are available, they are not only in bad and non-functional state but also very obsolete

The following are the Researchers innovating solutions to current challenges of business education programme in Nigerian Tertiary educational system as to enhance employability and reduce unemployment rate of graduates from Nigerian tertiary institutions, the following solutions can be implemented as advised by educational planners:

Been a planner, specialists in business education programs within the diverse Nigerian tertiary educational framework should engage in collaborative partnerships with various organizations operating within their geographical domain. Udegbumam, Igomu, Enenchukwu and Igbinothodua (2019) further noted that the benefits of collaboration are enormous because it would enable students acquire industrial skills, develop work habits and instill positive attitude of students towards industries and business education in particular. For instance, the Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) constitutes a mandatory component of the business education curriculum that students are required to complete; however, in certain

institutions, numerous students encounter significant difficulties in securing placements for their industrial training. If the institution had established robust collaborations and partnerships, industries would likely be more inclined to accept and equip students with the essential skills required to thrive as employers of labor subsequent to graduation. Rotua (2017) reported that if there are fewer linkages between industry and academics, then the school will not be able to get practical exposure. Conversely, the current scenario reveals that those organizations willing to accept students often lack the commitment to provide the requisite training and skills, thereby impeding the advancement of business education programs in introducing innovative practices. The interaction between institutions of higher learning and employers in Industries and related business organizations represent a means of ensuring quality education training programmes. The challenge to business and industry to succeed in an increasingly competitive world market is contingent upon skilled personnel, who learn, grow and adapt to the changing markets and technologies (Okoro, 2015).

Business education students should be given a close monitoring, observation, assessment and evaluation regarding their practical courses be it compulsory or electives: It appears that specialists/ lecturers in business education at different Nigeria tertiary education system do not provide students with adequate and follow-up monitoring exercise, particularly during their practical coursework, thereby allowing them to proceed without sufficient supervision. Ubulom (2012) is of the view that whether conceptualized in broad or narrow scope, business education programme requires adequate evaluation in order to ensure the effectiveness of the programme and or ascertain the discrepancies in the programme and accordingly make decision(s). He also suggests that evaluation should be built into business education programme development processes, right from the beginning and be clearly designed, made simple, flexible, and realistic. Given that the students recognize this lack of oversight, they may prioritize merely securing grades rather than actively engaging in the essential practical competencies that need to be developed.

Business education programme experts in various Nigeria tertiary educational system should make sure they are involved in the curriculum planning and developing, especially the Professors in the field, Association of Business Education (ABEN) National Boards should also be involved in the designing of the programme to make sure the curriculum aligns with the industries needs so as to enable the graduates to get employment after graduation. Oguejiofor (2020) reported that curriculum offerings at the tertiary institution levels do not cater for some of the needs of the current century skills. In agreement, Furthermore, the incorporation of entrepreneurship education within the academic curriculum, as mandated by national policy directives, has the potential to cultivate innovative cognitive processes and entrepreneurial ambitions among students. According to Ezenwafor and Onokpaunu (2017), business education programme is a branch of vocational education concerned with exposing its recipients to the internal and external foundations and functioning of the workplace. Business education is a work-focused, skill-based, result-oriented and technology-based educational programme (Ugwoke, 2011). It is therefore expected for expert in the field to be present when designing the curriculum so as for it to be designed in a way and manner to achieve the aims and objectives of the programme.

Conclusion

The study investigated the challenges of business education programme in Nigerian educational system and proffer innovating solutions by educational planners which helps in addressing the challenges of Business Education Programme in Nigerian educational system by integrating the programme and give the nation's economic high hope and understanding the ways in tackling the global poverty of students after graduation by been an employer of labour through education in Nigeria. The integration of Business Education Programme into the Nigeria educational system is basically for the economic transformation, Job creation and development in the country.

Recommendations

Based on the study the educational planners recommend the following to the business education programmes experts:

1. Specialists in business education programs within the diverse Nigerian tertiary educational framework should engage in collaborative partnerships with various organizations operating within their geographical domain.
2. Business education students should be given a close monitoring, observation, assessment and evaluation regarding their practical courses be it compulsory or electives
3. Business education programme experts in various Nigeria tertiary educational system should make sure they are involved in the curriculum planning and developing, especially the Professors in the field, Association of Business Education (ABEN) National Boards should also be involved in the designing of the programme.
4. Government should invest in the funding of the programme because the programme aim is basically for the economic transformation, Job creation and development in the country.

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